

Supporting Information Text S3: Biodiversity-assessment tools

We aimed for tools or methods returning a proxy for in situ biodiversity in a terrestrial ecosystem and excluded thus species identification mechanisms (e.g., iNaturalist, ObsIdentify), observation databases (e.g., observation.org, Global Biodiversity Information Facility) and habitat maps (e.g., Biological Valuation Map, Habitat Mapping Layer). We also excluded mathematical models without any user interface. A tool as such must be accessible to a wider audience than only researchers within the topic. The corresponding PRISMA-diagram is visualized below (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: PRISMA-diagram used for the review process. Search term used in the process were ¹: biodiversity AND ("tool" OR "platform" OR "calculator") AND ("agro-ecosystem" OR "agroecosystem" OR "agrosystems" OR "agroforestry" OR "hedgerow" OR "agriculture" OR "agricultural" OR "farmland" OR "farm") and ²: biodiversity AND ("tool" OR "platform" OR "calculator"). n reflects the amount of studies, # tools reflects the amount of tools extracted. Note that one study is able to report more than one tool (which is specified in Table 1) or that multiple studies can reflect to the same tool.

Initially, we performed a systematic search using the following terms: biodiversity AND ("tool" OR "platform" OR "calculator"), inserted in Web of Science Core collection and Scopus (December 2023). This resulted in 15460 and 20549 results, respectively. A lot of results corresponded with large-scale biodiversity assessments; thus we adapted our term to: biodiversity AND ("tool" OR "platform" OR "calculator") AND ("agro-ecosystem" OR "agroecosystem" OR "agrosystems" OR "agroforestry" OR "hedgerow" OR "agriculture" OR "agricultural" OR "farmland" OR "farm"). This resulted in 2809 and 2919 results, respectively. The high number of studies restricted us to review the 200 most relevant studies per database. We managed to extract 43 tools (that were mentioned, used or described in the studies) in this systematic process. This rather limited success could be caused by the term used: 'platform' often refers to databases, websites or policy concepts, 'calculator' can refer to mathematical models and 'tool' can refer to methods

for improving biodiversity, all apart from the interfaces we aim to target. Besides, our targeted kind of tools can be hidden in grey literature as well, hence not showing up in these scientific-based databases.

We additionally performed an additional query through Google Search Engine (with the adapted term) to check for additional records hidden in the grey literature. This resulted in 23 tools retrieved. Still, we argue that different interesting tools are not omitted at this stage, either due to the scope lying beyond agriculture only (e.g., Nature Smart Cities, EFA) or due to the name not implementing 'tool', 'platform' or 'calculator' (e.g., Biodiversity Metric).

We used personal knowledge to extend our database, along with tools suggested in the questionnaire (**Text S2**). This resulted in a total number of 73 tools considered in our database (**Table 1**). We want to emphasize that there are probably more suitable tools in existence, but this kind of evidence is very hard to retrieve in a holistic and systematic way. We however think that the set of tools listed below does contain a representative view on the different tool types around and hence are a sufficient set to use further on.

For each tool, we retrieved the year of last adaptation of the tools and classified their intended application environments (forest, agriculture, urban, aquatic, soil, overall, other). Furthermore, we classified the tools in different interface types via which they can be assessed, such as computer programs specifically designed for the tool (CP), spreadsheets (Excel), geographic information system-tools (QGIS), programming tools (R) and textual/literature guidelines (TG). We then assessed the scale of application. We distinguished three classes within the scale of application: (P) tools that only are applicable on the homogeneous plot- or field level, (L) tools that are applicable on regional or landscape level, but only enable large scale application and (F) tools functioning on farm or landscape level and where users thus can delineate the scale of application to own desire (**Fig. 2**).

Figure 2: Conceptual figure for the scale of application. Tools functioning on landscape scale only cannot assess detailed features within the pixel of assessment. Tools functioning on plot or field scale cannot zoom out to assess a landscape as such. Tools based on landscape scale are intermediate and can be used to assess more spatial complex units, such as farms.

Table 1: Overview of biodiversity tools to assess biodiversity in terrestrial ecosystems, along with main developers, country of origin and a link (*: retrieved with systematic search, °: retrieved with Google Search Engine, 1: mentioned in the review of (Stewart et al., 2022), 2: mentioned in the study of (Landert et al., 2020), 3: mentioned in the study of (Mondière et al., 2023), 4: mentioned in the study of (Braband et al., 2003), 5: mentioned in tool catalogue <https://biodiversitystrategytoolnavigator.thefashionpact.org/tool-catalogue/>). Apart from the systematic searches, we added several relevant tools that were mentioned during the performed questionnaire (°) or from personal knowledge of the authors (P), for proper distinguishing, we shaded the rows grey.

Abbreviation – Tool name	(main) Developers		Link
CPS – Credit Point System*		https://admin.ipsuisse.ch/	
Biodiversity metric ^P		https://publications.naturalengland.org.uk/publication/6049804846366720	
Nature Smart Cities ^P		?	https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/centres/environment-sustainable-development-research/projects/nature-smart-cities/
INVEST ^{*1}		https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest	
i-Tree Eco ^{*1}		https://www.itreetools.org/tools/i-tree-eco	
LUCI ^{*1}	LUCI	https://unstats.un.org/unsd/envaccounting/SeeaRev/meeting2013/EG13-BG-9.pdf	
ARIES for SEEA ^{*1}		?	https://aries.integratedmodelling.org/aries-for-seea-explorer/
ASSET ^P		https://assist.ceh.ac.uk/asset-v2	
Biodiversity Footprint Calculator ^{o5}		https://www.plansup.nl/biodiversity-footprint-calculator/	
QBS index ^P		https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167880904000970	
Greenspace Bird Calculator ^P		https://github.com/coreytcallaghan/urban_greenspaces	
EFA – Ecological Focus Area*	UH	?	http://sitem.herts.ac.uk/aeru/efa/
HFI – Healthy Farm Index ^{*o}		https://johnquinnv.wixsite.com/agroecology/healthy-farm-index	
Berger-Parker index ^P		https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4020-6865-2_3	
FQA - Floristic quality Assessment ^P		https://universalfqa.org/	
Habitat Hectares ^P		https://www.environment.vic.gov.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0016/91150/Vegetation-Quality-Assessment-Manual-Version-1.3.pdf	
CFT – Cool Farm Tool ^{*2o5}		https://coolfarm.org/the-tool/	
SMART Farm Tool ^{*2}	sfs FiBL		https://smart-farm.fibl.org/Account/Login?ReturnUrl=%2F
B-INTACT ^{o5}		?	https://www.fao.org/in-action/epic/ex-act-tool/suite-of-tools/b-intact/en/

GLOBIO *1°5		https://github.com/GLOBIO4/GlobioModelPublic/wiki	
IDA – Index of Agrobiodiversity*		https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.336	
TAPE – Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation*		?	https://www.fao.org/agroecology/tools-tape/en/
Nature value explorer ^Q		https://www.natuurwaaardeverkenner.be/#highlight	
Natur^{plus} standard ^Q		http://www.naturplus-standard.de/en/quantification-methods/biological-diversity	
Biodiversiteitsmonitor akkerbouw ^Q		https://www.boakkerbouw.nl/kennis-en-innovatie/pops-biodiversiteitsmonitor-akkerbouw	
BioBio Indicators ^P		https://www.agroscope.admin.ch/agroscope/en/home/topics/environment-resources/biodiversity-landscape/biodiversitaetsindikatoren/biobio.html	
LOOC-B ^o		https://looc-b.farm/about	
HNV – High Nature Value Index*		?	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.03.011
HNV – High Nature Value Indicators*		?	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.04.012
SALCA-BD – Swiss Agricultural LCA-Biodiversity*		https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.2c09677	
e-planner ^o		https://e-planner.ceh.ac.uk/About	
LEAP guideline*		?	https://doi.org/10.3390/su142316259
FABLE calculator ^o		?	https://pure.iiasa.ac.at/id/eprint/16934/ https://fableconsortium.org/tools/fablecalculators/
FBO-OLAP - Farmland Biodiversity Observatory Online Analytical Processing*		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2021.101231	
SWAT – Soil and Water Assessment Tool*		https://swat.tamu.edu/docs/	
QuestMEI - Mediterranean Ecological Infrastructure Quality Questionnaire*		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsv.2019.03.017	
ESAT-A – Ecosystem Services Assessment Tool for Agroforestry*		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2014.04.024	
BiolImpact*		https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11367-019-01627-5#MOESM1	
Ecobee*		https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.3896/IBRA.1.53.1.05	

EII – Ecosystem Integrity Index*		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.01.077	
IBA - Agri-environment Biodiversity Index*		?	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1470160X22006926
EI – Indicators of ecological integrity*³		https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2017.0433	
EP – Indicators of the index of ecological potential*³		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.111165	
AECM – Biodiversity assessment scheme*		?	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.105649
INSPIA model*		?	www.inspia-europe.eu
floristic-vegetational indexes*		https://www.academia.edu/78633164/Integrated_tools_and_methods_for_the_analysis_of_agro_ecosystems_functionality_through_vegetational_investigations	
Rise 3.0*		https://doi.org/10.3390/su10061792	
WFAS – whole farm assessment system*		https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-017-0198-2	
DAKIS*		https://adz-dakis.com/en/ https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ese.2023.100274	
Biodiversity Yardstick*⁴		https://gaia-biodiversity-yardstick.eu/	
KUL – Kriterien umweltverträglicher Landbewirtschaftung*⁴		?	https://www.openagrar.de/receive/timport_mds_00017317
Ecopoints Lower Austria*⁴		https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809(03)00101-4	
Halberg*⁴			https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809(99)00055-9
Solagro*⁴		https://solagro.org/index.php	
Frieben*⁴			https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809(03)00101-4
Naturbilanz*⁴		https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809(03)00101-4	
ArEco*		?	https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-021-02191-x
Viva Grass Tool*		?	https://vivagrass.eu/
HBAT - Habitat and Biodiversity Assessment Tool°		https://www.canadianfga.ca/en/projects/habitat-biodiversity-assessment-tool/	
MEbA biodiversity platform°		https://unepmeba.org/biodiversity-platform/	
CAFRE BIO°		https://www.cafre.ac.uk/business-support/agriculture/environment/environment-technical-support/cafre-farm-biotool/	

BPT - Biodiversity Performance Tool° BMS – Biodiversity Monitoring system°⁵		?	https://bpt.biodiversity-performance.eu/pages/presentation https://bms.biodiversity-monitoring.info/node/1
ABC-map°		?	https://abc-map.fao.org/
FBS – Farm Biodiversity Scotland°		https://www.nature.scot/professional-advice/social-and-economic-benefits-nature/natural-capital/farming-nature	
PBF – Product Biodiversity Footprint°		?	http://www.productbiodiversityfootprint.com/
NZ-BAT – NZ Biodiversity Assessment Tool°		https://landcare.shinya.pps.io/BiodivPrototype/	
MAGIC°		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4095548	
ABDi°⁵			https://diversitylighthouse.org/abd_index
BIM – Biodiversity Impact Metric°⁵			https://www.cisl.cam.ac.uk/system/files/documents/measuring-business-impacts-on-nature.pdf
DIALECTE°⁵		http://dialecte.solagro.org/	
BII – Biodiversity Intactness Index°⁵			https://tnfd.global/tools-platforms/local-biodiversity-intactness-index/
BNGC - Biodiversity Net Gain Calculator°⁵		https://www.arcadis.com/en/insights/blog/belgium/hans-van-gossum/2023/measure-and-manage-the-impact-of-your-business-on-biodiversity	
STAR – Species Threat Abatement and Restoration metric°⁵			https://www.iucnredlist.org/assessment/star

In the second screening, we further selected tools that might be able to assess biodiversity in agroforestry systems specifically and removed tools not publicly assessable or focusing on too specific groups (fish, honeybees), not relevant to biodiversity in general or to biodiversity functional to agroforestry systems (**Table 2**). This resulted into a list of 37 distinct tools.

Table 2: Reasons of exclusion at full text stage. Green: retained tools for our study, Red: tools that were excluded.

Tool	Suitable to agriculture	Agroforestry-applicable	No relevant biodiversity output	Restricted access
CPS				
Biodiversity metric				
Nature Smart Cities				
INVEST		no		
i-Tree Eco	no			
LUCI		no		
ARIES	no			
ASSET				

Biodiversity Footprint Calculator	
QBS index	
Greenspace bird calculator	
EFA	
HFI	no
Berger-Parker index	
FQA	
Habitat Hectares	
CFT	
SMART Farm Tool	Toolkits or administrative suggestions
B-INTACT	
GLOBIO	
TAPE	no
Nature Value explorer	no
Naturplus-Standard	Toolkits or administrative suggestions
Index of agrobiodiversity	
Biodiversity Monitor for Arable Farming	no
BioBio indicators	Toolkits or administrative suggestions
LOOC-B	
HNV index	
HNV indicators	
SALCA-BD	
e-planner	no
LEAP guideline	no
FABLE calculator	no
FBO-OLAP	
SWAT	Fish only
QuestMEI	
ESAT-A	
BiolImpact	no
Ecobee	honeybee only
EII	
IBA	
EI	no
EP	no
AECM	
INSIA	
floristic-vegetational indexes	
RISE3.0	
WGAS	
DAKIS	
Biodiversity Yardstick	Currently unavailable
KUL	Not assessable
Ecopoints Lower austria	Not assessable
Halberg	Not assessable
Solagro	Not assessable
Friebe	Not assessable

Naturbilanz		Not assessable
ArEco	no	
Viva Grass	no	
HBAT		
MEbA		Not assessable
CAFRE BIO		
BPI		
ABC-map	no	
FBS		Currently unavailable
PBF		
NZ-BAT		
MAGIC	no	
ABDi	no	
BIM	no	
DIALECTE		
BII		
BNGC		Not assessable
STAR		Extinction risk is no proxy for biodiversity

For these 37 tools, we categorized the input-output relations in different categories (**Table 3**). Furthermore, the tools were evaluated on their open source-availability and whether they were applicable to a European scope. **Table 4** provides clarifications when a simple 0 or 1 was not justified.

Table 3: Categorizations created for available biodiversity tools. Applicability: the woody structures that a tool is using in its process. Input: the different input types that a tool is using. Output: the different output types that a tool gives.

Applicability	Input	Output
Tree: The feasibility of implementing scattered or solitary trees.	Woody: The input requires at least a basic distinction of woody features. This can emerge as different types or as in-type specification (structure, species).	Metric of biodiversity (MetricBio): The output consists of a proxy for total biodiversity (at least defined by a proper corresponding landscape value such as habitat diversity).
Hedge: The feasibility of implementing hedges/hedgerows.	Farm characteristics (FarmChar): The input requires farm characteristics, those can include farmland habitats, farm features, farm management, ...	Metric of a species group (MetricSpGr): The output consists of a proxy for at least 1 specific biodiversity group (at least defined by a proper corresponding variable such as predation or pollination).
Agroforestry (AF): The feasibility of implementing agroforestry in general (this category contains the agglomerate of SP, SA and FF).	Maps: The input requires maps of the study site itself, which can be used to define in-situ habitat composition and/or complexity, biotic occurrences, ...	Effect of agroforestry (EffAF): The output consists of biodiversity differences provoked by different woody feature implementation or at least offers the option to do so.
Silvopasture (SP): The feasibility of implementing silvopastoral systems. These can be applied as well through a pasture layer and sole trees or tree rows within.	Biodiversity characterization (BioChar): The input requires abundance or presence-absence data for at least one species group.	Proposed actions (PropAct): The output consists of actions that can be implemented to boost biodiversity levels or at least offers the option to identify these.
Silvoarable (SA): The feasibility of implementing silvoarable systems. These can be applied as well through arable layers and sole trees or tree rows within.	Landscape structure (LndscpCompl): The input requires maps of the surrounding landscape for the study site to enable ex-situ landscape complexity calculation.	
Food forest (FF): The feasibility of implementing food forests or similar systems (berry gardens).		
Forest grazing (FG): The feasibility of implementing grazed forests		

Table 4: Reasons to use a value of 0.5 and handling of topics not present in the questionnaire.

Driver	Explanation
Plot	<i>If the tool itself is landscape-based, but provides sufficient clarification in its guidelines to make it possible to use it for one plot only, for example when the output values per habitat are given.</i>
Farm	<i>If the tool itself is landscape-based, but provides sufficient clarification in its guidelines to make it possible to use it for a farm and its specific lay-out, for example when the output values per habitat are given.</i>
Free_Av	<i>If the tool itself is not freely available, but the guidelines provide sufficient info to assess a landscape following its protocol.</i>
LndscpCompl	<i>The tool makes use of maps stating the environment of the assessed area, without specifying the implementation of landscape complexity.</i>
MetricBio	<i>The tool returns a proxy for a metric relatable to biodiversity, but does not relate directly to biodiversity (habitat diversity, habitat connectivity)</i>
MetricSpGr	<i>The tool returns a proxy for a metric relatable to a biodiversity group, but does not relate directly to it (pollination) or only uses a limited amount of specific species</i>
Questionnaire: Textual guidance & LandsCompl	<p><i>Two topics were not assessed during the questionnaire: whether textual guidance is needed and whether the integration of landscape complexity is important. Both were set to a value of 1 (textual guidance is indispensable in scientific research and this manuscript aims to make the point about the necessity of integrating landscape into tools).</i></p>
Questionnaire: Agroforestry types	<p><i>One question in the questionnaire tackled agroforestry types, although defined more broadly. Therefore, we grouped these types to our defined types as follows:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tree: Increasing tree cover on farm • Hedge: Hedges, Riparian buffer strips, Shelterbelts and windbreaks • SA: Alley cropping, Silvoarable system • SP: Wood pasture, grazed orchard and woodland, Dehesa and montado, Silvopastoral system • FF: Regenerative farming, kitchen gardens, Forest gardening, Biodynamic orchard • FG: Farm woodland (forest grazing was not specifically tackled)

The result of this assessment is added in **Table 5** and visualized via non-metric multidimensional scaling.

Table 5: Overview of characteristics of 37 tools enabling biodiversity assessment in agroecosystems with agroforestry. Type: type of interface (WT = webtool, S = spreadsheet, GIS = geographic information system-tool, R = programming tool, TG = guidelines, CP = computer program). Scale: scale the tool is applicable to; please note that farm scale tools are highly flexible and as such applicable at the plot or regional scale (F = farm scale, L = landscape/regional scale, P = plot/field scale). Applicability: the agroforestry element that a tool is using in its process (Hedge = hedgerows, AF = agroforestry, SP = Silvopasture, SA = silvoarable, FF = food forest, FG = forest grazing). Input: the different input types that a tool is using (Woody = implementation of basic characterization for woody component, FarmChar = checklist of farm characteristics, Maps = habitat/environment mapping, BioChar = checklist for biotic indicators, LndscpCompl = landscape structure). Output: the different output types a tool gives (MetricBio = one global metric for overall biodiversity, MetricSpGr = one or more metrics for specific species groups, EffAF = effects of different agroforestry types, PropAct = proposed actions towards improving biodiversity). (°: assigned when a tool is not publicly assessable, *: assigned when a tool was not suited to European context). When characterizations were not fully integrated, but for which a proxy is taken into account (Supplementary Methods Text S3), these are displayed in grey. POV = point of view.

Tool	Type	Scale	Applicability	Input	Output
CPS	WT, TG	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge	Woody, FarmChar	MetricBio
Biodiversity metric	S, TG	P, F, L	AF, Tree, Hedge, SP, SA, FF	Woody, Maps	MetricBio, EffAF
Nature Smart Cities 1	S, TG	P, F, L	Tree	Woody, Maps	MetricBio, MetricSpGr, PropAct
Nature Smart Cities 2	S, TG	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge, FF	Woody, FarmChar	MetricBio, MetricSpGr, PropAct
ASSET	WT	L	AF	FarmChar, Maps	MetricBio, MetricSpGr
Biodiversity Footprint Calculator	WT, TG	P, F, L	AF	FarmChar, Maps	MetricBio
QBS	TG	P	AF	FarmChar, BioChar	MetricBio
EFA	CP, TG	P, F, L	AF, Tree, Hedge, SP, SA	Woody, FarmChar	MetricBio, MetricSpGr, EffAF
Habitat Hectares	TG	P, F, L	AF, Tree, SP	Woody, Maps	MetricBio
CFT	WT	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge	LndscpCompl, Woody, FarmChar	MetricSpGr
B-INTACT	CP, TG	P, F, L	AF	FarmChar, Maps	MetricBio
GLOBIO	CP, TG	P, F, L	AF	Maps	metricBio, MetricSpGr
Birdscalculator	R, TG	P	AF	BioChar	MetricBio
Index of agrobiodiversity	TG	P, F, L	Tree	FarmChar	MetricBio
Berger-Parker	TG	P	AF	FarmChar, BioChar	MetricBio
LOOC-B	WT, TG	P, F, L	AF	Maps, BioChar	MetricBio
HNV index	TG	F, L	Hedge	LndscpCompl, FarmChar	MetricBio
HNV indicators	TG	F, L	AF, Hedge, SP	LndscpCompl, FarmChar	MetricBio
SALCA-BD°	CP, TG	P, F, L	AF, Tree, Hedge, SP, SA	FarmChar	MetricBio, MetricSpGr, EffAF
FBO-OLAP°	TG	P, F, L	Hedge	LndscpCompl, FarmChar, BioChar	MetricBio

QuestMEI	TG	P	Hedge, SP	LndscpCompl, Woody, FarmChar, BioChar	MetricBio
ESAT-A°	TG	P	AF, SP	BioChar	MetricBio
EII*	TG	P	AF	Woody, BioChar	MetricBio
IBA	TG	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge, SP, FF	FarmChar, BioChar	MetricBio
AECM	TG	P, F, L	AF	FarmChar, BioChar	MetricBio
INSIA	WT, TG	P, F, L	AF, Hedge, SP	LndscpCompl, FarmChar	MetricBio
RISE3.0	CP, TG	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge, SP	FarmChar	MetricBio
WFAS	TG	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge	Woody, FarmChar	MetricBio
DAKIS	WT, TG	L	Hedge	LndscpCompl, FarmChar	MetricBio
HBAT°	WT, TG	F, L		Maps, BioChar	MetricSpGr, PropAct
FQA	TG	P	AF	BioChar	MetricBio
floristicVegIndex	TG	P	AF	BioChar	MetricBio
CAFRE BIO	S, TG	P, F, L	AF, Hedge, SP, SA	FarmChar	MetricBio, PropAct
BPI	WT, TG	P, F, L	AF, Tree, Hedge, SP	LndscpCompl, Woody, FarmChar, Maps, BioChar	PropAct
PBF	WT, TG	L	AF	FarmChar	MetricBio
NZ-BAT	WT, TG	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge	FarmChar	MetricBio, MetricSpGr
DIALECTE	TG	P, F, L	Hedge	FarmChar	MetricBio
BII	WT, TG	L	AF	Maps, BioChar	MetricBio

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